

Prediction of Subgrade California Bearing Ratio Using Falling Weight Deflectometer for Pavement Evaluation in Kenya

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Abstract: This study aimed to develop a method for determining the California Bearing Ratio of subgrade soils during pavement evaluations without the need for traditional, destructive trenching and laboratory testing. Subgrade California Bearing Ratio is a key parameter for assessing pavement foundation strength, with the Road Design Manual classifying subgrades from S1 to S6 based on California Bearing Ratio values. Eighteen road sections were purposively selected for analysis due to data availability, including Falling Weight Deflectometer readings, trench logs, laboratory soil tests, and construction data. Falling Weight Deflectometer data was collected at 100-meter intervals using a PRIMAX Falling Weight Deflectometer device, while trial pits were excavated every 5 km for sampling and laboratory testing. Soil classification followed the Unified Soil Classification System, with Lean Clay and Elastic Silt being predominant. Plasticity Index, Optimum Moisture Content, and Maximum Dry Density ranged from 7–23%, 12–27%, and 1250–1821 kg/m³ respectively. For modeling purposes, deflections from the 4th geophone (D4), positioned 600 mm from the load center, were selected due to consistent curve behavior in deflection bowl and surface modulus graphs. The laboratory-derived California Bearing Ratio values served as the dependent variable. Data from all road sections were randomly split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets. Models developed included Linear Regression, Random Forest, and Artificial Neural Networks. These models yielded R² values between 0.55 and 0.61, and Root Mean Square Errors of 7 to 7.2, indicating acceptable predictive performance. Predicted California Bearing Ratio values showed strong correlation with laboratory values, with Pearson correlation coefficients ranging from 0.81 to 0.84. The results demonstrate that Falling Weight Deflectometer data, particularly from the D4 geophone, can effectively be used to estimate subgrade California Bearing Ratio, offering a viable, non-destructive alternative for pavement evaluation.

Keywords: California Bearing Ratio, Elastic Silt, Falling Weight Deflectometer, Lean Clay, Unified Soil Classification System, Sub-grade.

1. Introduction

Subsoil condition is a key factor that is considered in design and performance of flexible pavement structures. The foundation is the platform on which the pavement is constructed. The first step in pavement design is determination of the alignment soils properties and the design traffic. A critical component studied during pavement evaluation is the subgrade material properties which are obtained using destructive methods of trenching to obtain samples for laboratory California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests or Dynamic Cone Penetrometer (DCP) tests inside the test pits (G.O.K, 2025b). The most important characteristic of the subgrade is the elastic modulus which, according to the Road Design Manual (Part 3), was found to be fairly complicated and time-consuming. A correlation between CBR range and elastic modulus obtained using plate bearing tests as outlined in G.O.K, 1987. The new Road Design Manual Volume 3 specifies the subgrade strength in terms of CBR and provides a range of subgrade classes from S1 to S6 with the median CBR ranging from 3.5 to 45 (G.O.K, 2025a). Falling Weight Deflectometer (FWD), which is superior to plate bearing test, is a non-destructive testing method widely used for assessing pavement structural condition and properties. It applies a dynamic load to the

pavement surface and measures the resulting deflections. FWD testing is rapid, efficient, and can be performed in situ, providing real-time data on pavement response to loading. It applies a dynamic load to the pavement surface and measures the resulting deflections. Predicting subgrade CBR using FWD has the potential to streamline pavement rehabilitation design and management processes. Engineers could use FWD data collected during routine pavement evaluations to assess subgrade conditions, identify areas of concern, and make informed decisions regarding pavement rehabilitation or maintenance strategies. There is a need to address pressing issues in pavement engineering and infrastructure management, including the demand for rapid and cost-effective methods, limited accessibility to real-time data, advancements in non-destructive testing techniques, and the desire for enhanced pavement management practices. By tackling these issues, this study aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge and practice in pavement engineering and infrastructure management.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The study utilized secondary data which included FWD data, trenching logs, laboratory results and construction data. Subgrade materials had been extracted from 1m by 1m by approximately 1.5m deep trenches dug on the road shoulders and the samples were delivered in sealed sampling bags to the laboratory. CBR was then obtained by considering the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content determined from the Proctor test (Mugai et al., 2020). After the samples were extracted, the trenches were covered using nearby materials which were compacted in layers using a vibrating hammer. The top surface was protected using concrete. FWD data was obtained using FWD equipment.

2.2 Selection of models

The subgrade surface modulus was first computed using the formula:

$$\text{Subgrade Surface Modulus } E_n = ((1-0.35^2) \times 150 \times 150 \times P) / 200 \times G_n$$

Where:

P is the contact pressure in kPa

150 is the diameter of the load plate

G_n is the deflection at each offset distance from 200mm to 2100mm from the centre of the load plate

A different formula was used to compute the subgrade surface modulus on the first geophone sensor as follows:

$$\text{Subgrade Surface Modulus } E_o = (2(1-0.35^2) \times 150 \times P) / G_o$$

Where:

G_o is the deflection at the load plate position

Subgrade modulus was important in finding out the strength of the subgrade soil and the behavior of the material which would then inform the model to be developed.

2.3 Developing the predictive models

Regression analysis was used to identify the relationships between two variables and to predict a variable. Regressions can be linear regressions or non-linear regressions. The regression can also be a simple linear regression or multiple linear regressions for identifying relationships for more variables (Hui, 2018).

A multiple regression model was developed by considering various independent variables such as contact pressure, air temperature, MDD and OMC. The CBR which was considered in developing the model was the actual CBR obtained from the laboratory tests of materials from trenches. After training and testing the model, values of y were predicted by inputting values in x.

In addition to the regression model, other models were developed using machine learning tools. They are Random Forest (RF) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN).

2.4 Validating the predictive models

Validation of the predictive models was done to ensure that the models are accurate. External validation was carried out by splitting the data set into two; training (model development) and test (model validation) samples using a random process. In this case, 80% of data from a road section was used as for training the models and the remaining 20% for testing the models. The R^2 score (coefficient of determination) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) were used as a measure of the models' predictive ability.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Deflection bowls

Deflection bowls were developed for all road sections in order to study the behaviour of deflections and find out the trend of deflections in relation to the geophone position. A sample of the deflection bowls are presented in Figure 1

Figures 1 Deflection bowls

Readings from the fourth geophone, D4, which is located at 600mm from the centre of the plate were used to develop the models because as observed from most of the deflection bowls, that was the point where the deflection curves changed and started tapering off;

3.2 Deflection ratios

The deflection ratios were obtained for Road section 1 to 18 in order to find out linearity or non-linearity behaviour of the materials which would aid in making a decision on the most appropriate model. The deflection ratios for D4/D3 and D5/D4 were 1.45 and 2.41 respectively. This variance indicated non-linearity behaviour of the materials and therefore the most appropriate model would not be a linear model.

3.3 Subgrade Surface Modulus

Figure 2 shows the graphical representation of the subgrade surface modulus.

Figure 2 Surface Modulus

The surface modulus decreased as the stress decreased but at around D4, which is located at 600mm from the loading plate, the surface modulus started to increase as the stress decreased. These findings slightly differed from those of Chai et al., 2013 who found that the Surface Modulus was decreasing as the stress level decreased at a distance about 450 mm from the centre of the loading plate and beyond 450mm, the Surface Modulus increased as the stress level decreased. This study, just like for Chai et al., found this behaviour of the material to signify non-linearity of the material;

3.4 Model development using regression models

Three models were developed using Linear regression (LR), Random Forest (RF) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The data used in the model development was combined data from all the road sections. The data was split into two; 80% used for training the model and 20% used for testing the model.

The dependent variables considered for model development were Deflections at 600mm, Contact Pressure and Air Temperature, MDD and OMC variables.

The only model with a direct formula for computing CBR was the LR model. The RF and ANN models are obtained using machine learning tool which is system based and require the prediction to be carried out using a relevant software. The statistical analysis of predicted CBR using the three models is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1 Statistical analysis of predicted CBR using Random Forest, Linear Regression and Artificial Neural Networks models

Independent Variables used in developing the model	STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PREDICTED CBR USING VARIOUS MODELS								
	Pearson's Coeff			R2 Score			RMSE		
	RF	LR	ANN	RF	LR	ANN	RF	LR	ANN
Deflections, Contact Pressure and Air Temperature, MDD and OMC	0.8229	0.8435	0.8131	0.5747	0.6106	0.5917	7.2873	6.9733	7.1408

The values of CBR predicted using the various models are presented in Table 1

- i. Machine learning was found to be a powerful tool for developing predictive models with higher accuracy of prediction. Random Forest and Artificial Neural Networks models were developed in addition to multiple linear regression. This finding was similar to (Habal et al., 2025) who sought to find out the application of machine learning techniques for CBR prediction and found machine learning offered potential in predicting CBR with higher accuracy and efficiency;
- ii. R² Score (Coefficient of Determination) measured how well the models explained the variability of the Lab CBR. The Models explained 57% to 61% of the variance which made them the appropriate models; and,
- iii. (Root Mean Squared Error) showed the average error in predicted CBR therefore lower values are better. The LR model was found to have the lowest RMSE value of 6.97.

Table 2: Predicted CBR using Random Forest, Linear Regression and Artificial Neural Networks models

Actual Lab CBR	Predicted Lab CBR (RF) – Model 4	Predicted Lab CBR (LR) – Model 5	Predicted Lab CBR (ANN) – Model 6
13	12	12	10
7	8	10	9

Actual Lab CBR	Predicted Lab CBR (RF) – Model 4	Predicted Lab CBR (LR) – Model 5	Predicted Lab CBR (ANN) – Model 6
6	8	7	7
19	21	21	21
11	13	13	13
11	12	12	10
7	13	14	12
8	13	11	10
16	14	20	20
13	14	13	13
18	14	13	10
4	12	11	12
30	13	12	13
55	28	30	29
14	13	13	12
35	32	29	32
30	23	26	24
9	11	13	11
16	11	12	18
16	14	17	16
12	12	14	16
13	7	10	9
6	10	7	6
8	9	9	10
8	13	12	11

- i. The Pearson correlation coefficient, often denoted as 'r', measures the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables. Values range from -1 to +1. A value of +1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates no correlation. All models indicated positive correlation;

4. Conclusion

From the results obtained, the three models were found to predict CBR fairly accurately. The RF and ANN models can be used with the help of appropriate software like python. The LR model which had the highest values for R^2 and lowest RMSE hence was found to be the best prediction model. This finding is in agreement with Harrell, 2015 who indicated that the ordinary multiple linear regression model is frequently used and has parameters that are easily interpreted. The CBR predictions from this model had the highest Pearson's correlation coefficient hence they were 84.5% similar to the CBR values obtained from the lab. The model was as follows:

- i. Model No. 5

$$\text{CBR} = 5.2215 + (-0.0036 * D4) + (-0.0144 * \text{Contact Pressure}) + (-0.2522 * \text{Air Temperature}) + (0.0233 * \text{MDD}) + (-0.3732 * \text{OMC})$$

Where:

- D4 are the normalized deflections in μm recorded on the 4th geophone which is 600mm from the centre of the loading plate;
- Contact pressure is recorded in the FWD file in kPa;
- Air Temperature is recorded in the FWD file during the study in $^{\circ}\text{C}$
- MDD is the material Maximum Dry Density; and,
- OMC is the Optimum Moisture Content.

The MDD and OMC can be obtained from various sources as follows:

- i. Past pavement record charts prepared during construction; and,
- ii. Non-destructive methods such as Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), Nuclear Density Gauge (NDG) and Light Weight Deflectometers (LWD) can be used to determine subgrade MDD and OMC.

5. Recommendations and Scope for Further Work

The following recommendations are made:

- i. The developed predictive models can be subjected to further validation by using them to predict CBR from other road sections in future pavement evaluations;
- ii. The models can be refined further with additional data sets; and,
- iii. The effect of depth of subgrade materials from the surface can be studied and incorporated in future models. The depth of subgrade can be established using non-

Conflict of Interest: There are no potential conflicts of interest present in this study.

Data Availability: Data will be available upon request.

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